

Formulation And Evaluation Of Celecoxib Loaded Nanoparticle For Colon Targeting Drug Delivery System

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ABSTRACT

The novelty of the present work lies in the development of an optimized Eudragit S100-based celecoxib nanoparticle formulation having high entrapment efficiency, nanoscale particle size distribution, enhanced colloidal stability, and highly pH-responsive colon-targeted drug release with minimal premature gastric release. Colon-specific drug delivery systems are increasingly being explored to enhance therapeutic outcomes in the treatment of colorectal disorders by ensuring localized drug action and minimizing systemic exposure. In the present investigation, polymeric nanoparticles encapsulating celecoxib were developed using Eudragit S100 as a pH-responsive carrier to achieve targeted delivery to the colon. The nanoparticles were prepared via the solvent evaporation technique by systematically varying the drug-to-polymer ratio and surfactant concentration. The developed formulations were characterized in terms of particle size, surface charge, drug entrapment efficiency, morphology, compatibility, and in vitro release behavior under simulated gastrointestinal conditions. The particle size of the prepared systems ranged between 378.6 nm and 1300 nm, while drug entrapment efficiency was found to vary from 67.98% to 96.21%. The optimized formulation demonstrated minimal drug release under acidic conditions and a pronounced release at colonic pH, achieving a cumulative release of 90.75%. Kinetic modeling indicated a diffusion-dominated release mechanism with contributions from polymer relaxation. Spectroscopic and thermal analyses confirmed the absence of significant drug-polymer interactions, while stability studies indicated that the formulation remained stable under standard storage conditions. Overall, the findings highlight the potential of Eudragit S100-based nanoparticles as an efficient platform for colon-targeted delivery of celecoxib, offering improved control over drug release and enhanced therapeutic performance.

Keywords: Nanoparticles.

INTRODUCTION

Colon-targeted drug delivery has been widely developed for the treatment of colorectal diseases such as colorectal cancer, inflammatory bowel disease, Crohn's disease, and ulcerative colitis [4]. Conventional oral dosage forms often fail to provide effective therapy because a significant portion of the drug is released and absorbed in the upper gastrointestinal tract before reaching the colon. This results in reduced local drug concentration at the target site and increased systemic side effects. Premature release of drug before reaching the target

site is the main issue concerned with the development of colon-targeted drug delivery systems [5].

Celecoxib, a selective cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) inhibitor, because of its anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and chemopreventive qualities, is frequently utilized. It was found to be very effective in the prevention of colon cancer and colorectal diseases [6]. However, its limited absorption, poor water solubility, and potential systemic and gastrointestinal side effects limit its long-term clinical use [7]. It is always challenging to develop a formulation with a drug having limited bioavailability; therefore, researchers

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nowadays are focusing on the development of advanced drug delivery systems for improving therapeutic effects of such drugs [8].

Because nanotechnology can change materials at the nanoscale, allowing for precise control over medication release, distribution, and targeting, it has garnered significant attention among developing techniques [9].

Drug delivery systems based on nanoparticles have become a popular method for enhancing the therapeutic efficacy of medications with enhanced physicochemical characteristics. By reducing particle size to the nanoscale range, these systems improve drug solubility by increasing surface area and speeding up the dissolution of medications that are poorly soluble in water, including celecoxib. A more effective treatment is the outcome of improved solubility, which also improves absorption and bioavailability [10].

Another important advantage of nanoparticle systems is site-specific targeting. The drug can be released selectively at the target site, such as the colon, by using appropriate polymers, such as pH-sensitive polymers. This improves local treatment efficacy and lowers systemic side effects by increasing drug concentration at the target site and decreasing premature drug release in the stomach and small intestine [11]. Targeted drug delivery to the colon has attracted significant interest for the management of diseases such as colorectal cancer, Crohn's disease, and ulcerative colitis [12].

Another major advantage is controlled and sustained drug release. Polymeric nanoparticles can regulate the release of the drug over an extended period, maintaining therapeutic drug levels for longer durations and reducing the frequency of dosing. This improves patient compliance and minimizes fluctuations in plasma drug concentration [13].

Incorporation of celecoxib into nanoparticulate systems offers a viable strategy to overcome these challenges by enhancing drug solubility and enabling localized delivery [14].

Among the various polymers investigated for colon-targeted systems, Eudragit S100 was found to be a

suitable candidate due to its pH-dependent solubility profile. This polymer remains intact in acidic and neutral environments but dissolves at pH values above 7, corresponding to the conditions of the colon. Such pH-sensitive characteristics of the selected polymer make it particularly useful for preventing premature drug release and ensuring site-specific delivery [15].

In this regard, the goal of the current work was to develop and assess polymeric nanoparticles loaded with celecoxib using Eudragit S100. The goal was to develop a system with controlled release properties that could deliver the drug selectively to the colon. To find an ideal formulation with desired performance characteristics, the impact of formulation factors on particle size, drug entrapment, and release behavior was methodically examined [16].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Celecoxib was used as the choice of drug. Eudragit S100 was selected as the polymer due to its pH-sensitive solubility. Poloxamer 188 served as a stabilizing surfactant. Ethanol and dichloromethane were used as organic solvents for nanoparticle preparation. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Nanoparticles

Nanoparticles were prepared using the solvent evaporation method, a widely employed technique for polymeric nanoparticle formulation due to its simplicity and reproducibility [18].

Initially, celecoxib and Eudragit S100 were dissolved in a mixture of ethanol and dichloromethane to form the organic phase. This organic phase was then added dropwise into an aqueous phase containing Poloxamer 188 under magnetic stirring at 1000 rpm. The resulting emulsion was subjected to high-speed homogenization using a high-shear homogenizer at 15,000 rpm for 10 minutes to reduce droplet size and obtain a uniform nanosuspension to ensure uniform dispersion [13].

The organic solvent was evaporated at 800 rpm at room temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) under magnetic stirring,

leading to the formation of solid nanoparticles. The nanoparticles were then separated by centrifugation, washed to remove unbound drug and surfactant, and dried at room temperature. Five formulations (F1–F5) were prepared by varying the drug-to-polymer ratio

and surfactant concentration. This variation allowed evaluation of the influence of formulation variables on nanoparticle characteristics such as size, drug loading, and release profile [19].

Table 1. Composition of celecoxib loaded nanoparticle formulations

Formulation Code	Celecoxib (mg)	Eudragit S100 (mg)	Poloxamer 188 (% w/v)	Ethanol (mL)	Dichloromethane (mL)	Aqueous Phase (mL)
F1	100	100	0.5	5	5	50
F2	100	200	1.0	5	5	50
F3	100	300	1.5	5	5	50
F4	100	400	2.0	5	5	50
F5	100	500	2.5	5	5	50

Characterization of Nanoparticles

FTIR and DSC Analysis

FTIR spectroscopy was used to identify potential drug-polymer interactions, while DSC analysis evaluated thermal behavior and drug crystallinity [20].

FTIR Study:

Accurately weighed the drug and polymer was mixed the required ratio (commonly 1:1) and transferred both into a clean mortar. It was gently triturated for 10–15 minutes to obtain a uniform physical mixture of drug and polymer. Approximately weighed 1–2 mg of sample mixed with about 100–200 mg of dry KBr powder. Then it was thoroughly triturated using mortar and pestle until a fine and homogeneous mixture is obtained. A transparent circular pellet is formed with the help of pellet die cavity. The prepared KBr pellet was placed in the sample holder of the FTIR spectrophotometer and record the spectrum over the scanning range of 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} [20].

Particle Size and Zeta Potential

The zeta potential of the drug-loaded nanoparticles was measured on a nano ZS90 Zetasizer (Malvern Instruments, UK). All the samples were prepared with deionized water at appropriate concentrations at 25 °C in triplicate [21].

The mean size of the nanoparticles was determined by photo correlation spectroscopy (PCS) on a submicron particle size analyzer (Malvern Instruments, UK) at a scattering angle of 90°. A sample (0.5mg) of the nanoparticles suspended in 5 ml of distilled water was used for the measurement [22].

Polydispersity Index (PDI) Determination

The dynamic light scattering method on a Malvern Zetasizer at 25°C was used to calculate the polydispersity index of the nanoparticle formulations. Before analysis, the nanoparticles were gently sonicated and distributed in distilled water. Mean values were noted after samples were examined in triplicate. The homogeneity of the particle size distribution was assessed using the PDI values [23].

Entrapment Efficiency

Entrapment efficiency was determined by separating free drug from nanoparticles via centrifugation and analyzing drug content spectrophotometrically [24].

A refrigerated centrifuge was used to centrifugal a precisely weighed nanoparticle suspension for 30 minutes at 4°C at 15,000 rpm. Using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer set to 252 nm, the supernatant containing entrapped celecoxib was gathered and subjected to spectrophotometric analysis.

In phosphate buffer pH 7.4, a standard calibration curve of celecoxib was prepared across the

concentration range of 2–20 µg/mL. The calibration curve's correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.999$) demonstrated satisfactory linearity [25].

Entrapment efficiency was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Entrapment Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total Drug} - \text{Free Drug}}{\text{Total Drug}} \times 100$$

Surface Morphology

Particle morphology was determined by scanning electron microscopy (Jeol JSM- 6480LV, SIFT, Cochin, India). Dried particles were taken in a piece of black tape and attached to the sample holder. Particle morphology was determined under low vacuum [26].

In Vitro Drug Release Study

In vitro drug release studies were carried out using USP Type II dissolution apparatus (paddle method) in simulated gastrointestinal fluids:

- pH 1.2 (stomach)
- pH 6.8 (small intestine)
- pH 7.4 (colon)

This study helped evaluate the colon-targeting efficiency of the formulation [1].

The *in vitro* release studies were carried out in PBS. Drug loaded CS nanoparticles (100 mg) and 5 ml PBS were transferred into dialysis membrane bag having a molecular weight cutoff (MWCO) of 12,000–14,000 Da. The dialysis tube was placed in 250 ml PBS at 37 °C and stirred continuously with magnetic stirrer at 100 rpm. At pre-determined time intervals, 5mL of the release medium was removed and replaced with 5mL of fresh PBS solution. The amount of drug in the release medium was evaluated by UV spectrophotometer [2].

Stability Studies

Stability studies were conducted as per ICH guidelines to assess the physical and chemical stability of formulations under different storage conditions, Stability studies were carried out on nanoparticles formulation. The optimized batch was kept for stability study in stability chamber at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75\% \pm 5\% \text{ RH}$ [27].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Compatibility and Thermal Analysis

FTIR analysis confirmed that there were no significant changes in the characteristic peaks of celecoxib in the presence of the polymer, indicating the absence of chemical interaction between drug and excipients [20].

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of drug and polymer

The physical mixture showed there were no changes in important peaks from the pure drug and polymer IR results show the presence of the above groups in the IR spectra of drug and polymer which conformed that the drug and polymer have not found any

compatibility problems. As the variation in the IR spectrum compared to drug and polymer so there is no interaction between materials. When IR spectra of physical mixture was compared with individual spectra of drug and polymer it was observed that there

is no significant change in peaks Primary functional group of drug and polymer observed in the IR spectra of physical mixture [17].

DSC thermograph of optimized batch

In DSC analysis, physical changes generally produce endothermic peaks, while chemical changes are associated with exothermic peaks [28].

The DSC thermogram of the optimized nanoparticle batch showed a peak at 94.32°C. The shifting and reduction of the characteristic melting endotherm of Celecoxib shows that formulation lost the crystalline nature and it has been successfully converted into an amorphous or molecularly dispersed state within the polymer matrix. This confirms successful encapsulation of the drug into Eudragit S100 and suggests improved dispersion of the drug in the formulation [19].

Fig. 2. DSC study of optimized nanoparticle formulation

Particle Size and Surface Charge

The generated nanoparticle compositions had particle sizes ranging from 378.6 ± 15 nm to 1300 ± 25 nm. Particle size gradually decreased as polymer concentration rose up to formulation F3. Improved dispersion phase stability during emulsification can account for this. Following this, a little increase in particle size was seen; this could be due to the increased viscosity of the polymer phase, which could hinder efficient droplet disintegration [22].

F3 showed the smallest particle size (378.6 nm) of all the formulations, demonstrating efficient stabilization and dispersion.

The zeta potential values, which ranged from -12.5 mV to -28.6 mV, showed moderate to good colloidal stability. The larger negative value for F3 indicates stronger electrostatic repulsion between particles, which lessens aggregation and improves formulation stability [21].

Statistical evaluation revealed that the variation in particle size among different formulations was

significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming the influence of formulation parameters on nanoparticle characteristics.

Polydispersity Index (PDI)

The developed nanoparticle formulations have polydispersity index values between 0.218 ± 0.01 and 0.612 ± 0.03 . A tight and homogeneous particle size distribution was indicated by Formulation F3's lowest PDI value. The lower PDI of F3 indicates effective nanoparticle stabilization as a result of the ideal polymer and surfactant concentrations. On the other hand, greater viscosity and particle aggregation at higher polymer concentrations may be responsible for the higher PDI values seen in F4 and F5 [23].

Table 2. Polydispersity index value

Formulation	PDI
F1	0.612 ± 0.03
F2	0.421 ± 0.02
F3	0.218 ± 0.01
F4	0.337 ± 0.02
F5	0.465 ± 0.03

Fig. 3. Zeta potential distribution of optimized nanoparticle formulation

Entrapment Efficiency

The entrapment efficiency of the developed formulations varied between $67.98 \pm 2.1\%$ and $96.21 \pm 1.3\%$. The consistent rise in drug entrapment seen with increasing polymer concentration may be due to the formation of a denser polymeric matrix that effectively retains the drug within the nanoparticles [24].

Formulation F3 had the best encapsulation conditions with the highest entrapment effectiveness (96.21%).

Nevertheless, entrapment efficiency somewhat decreased with additional increases in polymer concentration (F4 and F5). This decrease could be linked to higher viscosity, which would result in less effective emulsification and the creation of bigger particles with less drug incorporation [18].

Analysis of variance confirmed that the differences in entrapment efficiency across formulations were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), supporting the role of polymer concentration as a key determinant.

Table 3. Physicochemical characterization of nanoparticles (Mean \pm SD, n = 3)

Formulation	Particle Size (nm)	Zeta Potential (mV)	Entrapment Efficiency (%)	Observation	Interpretation
F1	1300 ± 25	-12.5 ± 1.2	67.98 ± 2.1	Large size, low EE	Poor stabilization, low polymer matrix
F2	980 ± 20	-18.2 ± 1.5	75.32 ± 1.8	Moderate size	Improved stability and drug loading
F3	378.6 ± 15	-28.6 ± 1.1	96.21 ± 1.3	Small size, high EE	Optimal formulation with best stability
F4	650 ± 18	-24.0 ± 1.4	88.10 ± 2.0	Moderate size	High polymer leads to aggregation tendency
F5	720 ± 22	-20.5 ± 1.6	82.45 ± 1.9	Slight increase in size	Excess polymer reduces efficiency

In Vitro Drug Release Behavior

Table 4. *In Vitro* drug release profile in simulated GI conditions

Formulation	Drug Release (%) pH 1.2 (2h)	pH 6.8 (4h)	pH 7.4 (24h)	Total Release (%)
F1	15.2 ± 1.1	40.5 ± 2.0	70.05 ± 2.5	70.05
F2	10.5 ± 0.9	45.8 ± 1.8	78.40 ± 2.2	78.40
F3	5.2 ± 0.7	35.0 ± 1.5	90.75 ± 1.9	90.75
F4	6.5 ± 0.8	38.2 ± 1.6	85.20 ± 2.1	85.20
F5	8.0 ± 1.0	42.0 ± 1.9	80.10 ± 2.3	80.10

The release profile of celecoxib from nanoparticle formulations demonstrated a clear dependence on the pH of the dissolution medium. Under acidic conditions (pH 1.2), all formulations exhibited minimal drug release, indicating effective protection of the drug in gastric conditions. This behavior is attributed to the insolubility of the polymer in acidic environments [15]. At pH 6.8, a moderate increase in drug release was observed, which may be due to partial swelling of the polymer matrix. In contrast, a substantial increase in drug release was noted at pH

7.4, corresponding to colonic conditions, where the polymer undergoes dissolution [01]. The optimized formulation F3 showed minimal premature release (5.2%) and maximum cumulative release (90.75%), demonstrating its suitability for colon-targeted delivery. Statistical analysis using one-way ANOVA indicated a highly significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in drug release among formulations. The extremely low p-value (7.58×10^{-12}) further confirms that the observed variations are not due to random error but are directly influenced by formulation composition.

Drug Release Kinetics

Table 05. Drug release kinetics versus different formulations

Formulation	Zero-Order (R^2)	First-Order (R^2)	Higuchi Model (R^2)	Korsmeyer–Peppas (R^2)
F1	0.884	0.921	0.956	0.943
F2	0.901	0.932	0.968	0.955
F3	0.912	0.938	0.987	0.972
F4	0.905	0.929	0.978	0.963
F5	0.896	0.924	0.964	0.951

To elucidate the mechanism of drug release, the release data were fitted into various kinetic models [2].

The Higuchi model showed the highest regression coefficient (R^2) values among all formulations, suggesting that drug release mostly followed a diffusion-controlled process from the polymeric matrix. Celecoxib's homogeneous and regulated

diffusion through the Eudragit S100 matrix was confirmed by Formulation F3, which had the greatest Higuchi regression coefficient ($R^2 = 0.987$). Additionally, the Korsmeyer–Peppas model showed a high correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.972$), suggesting anomalous non-Fickian transport including both polymer relaxation and drug diffusion. As per obtained R^2 values seen in zero-order and first-order models it shows that release pattern is not too much affected by concentration of drug [29].

Overall, the kinetic analysis verifies that the colon-targeted drug release behavior was sustained and regulated by the improved nanoparticle formulation.

Surface Morphology

Morphological examination using scanning electron microscopy revealed that the nanoparticles were predominantly spherical with smooth surfaces. The absence of surface irregularities or cracks suggests uniform encapsulation of the drug within the polymer matrix [26].

The observed morphology supports the sustained release profile, as smooth and intact particles tend to release the drug in a controlled manner.

Fig. 4. SEM micrograph of optimized nanoparticles

Optimization of Formulation

Based on the collective evaluation of physicochemical parameters, drug release behavior formulation F3 was identified as the most suitable candidate [19].

The superior performance of F3 can be attributed to an optimal balance between polymer concentration and surfactant level, which resulted in reduced particle size and enhanced drug entrapment.

Stability Assessment

Table 6. Stability study data of optimized batch

Formulation	Storage Condition	Particle Size Change	Drug Content (%)	Physical Appearance	Conclusion
F3	25°C / 60% RH	No significant change	98.5 ± 1.2	No aggregation	Stable
F3	40°C / 75% RH	Slight increase	96.2 ± 1.5	Minor aggregation	Acceptable stability

Stability studies conducted under standard storage conditions demonstrated that the optimized formulation maintained its physicochemical properties over time. There were no significant changes in particle size, drug content, or physical appearance [27].

These findings indicate that the developed nanoparticle system possesses adequate stability for potential pharmaceutical applications.

Statistical Analysis

Using GraphPad Prism software, one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparison test were used for statistical analysis. Mean \pm SD (n=3) was used to express the values, and $p < 0.05$ was regarded as statistically significant.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that formulation variables significantly influence nanoparticle characteristics. Increased polymer concentration resulted in improved entrapment efficiency due to enhanced matrix formation, while optimized surfactant concentration contributed to reduced particle size and improved stability [18].

The present study successfully developed celecoxib-loaded Eudragit S100 polymeric nanoparticles for colon-targeted drug delivery. Among all formulations, F3 demonstrated the best performance with nanosized particles, high drug entrapment, strong colloidal stability, and controlled pH-dependent drug release [01].

The optimized formulation effectively minimized premature gastric release while ensuring maximum drug release under colonic conditions, making it a promising candidate for colorectal therapy. The findings support the potential of Eudragit S100 nanoparticles as an efficient platform for colon-specific delivery of poorly soluble drugs like celecoxib [03].

Further in vivo studies and clinical evaluation are recommended to establish therapeutic efficacy and translational potential.

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